

Clinical and Etiological Characteristics and Outcomes of Pediatric Status Epilepticus Patients in a Tertiary Care Pediatric Intensive Care Unit: A Prospective Observational Study

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Received: 15-04-2024 / Revised: 28-04-2024 / Accepted: 11-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This prospective observational study investigates the clinical and etiological profiles and outcomes of children with status epilepticus (SE) admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) over 12 months. A total of 100 patients were included, revealing that SE predominantly affects children aged 1 to 5 years, with generalized convulsive seizures being the most common type. The study identifies infections and metabolic disorders as the primary underlying causes. Outcomes showed that 80% of patients achieved complete resolution of SE, with only a small percentage experiencing severe neurological sequelae. These findings underscore the effectiveness of current management strategies and highlight areas for potential improvement in patient care.

Keywords: Status Epilepticus, Pediatric Intensive Care Unit, Clinical Profile, Etiology.

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) is a critical neurologic emergency characterized by a prolonged or repeated seizure activity that can lead to significant morbidity and mortality if not promptly managed [1]. It is particularly concerning in pediatric populations due to the potential for lasting neurological impairment and other severe complications [2]. The management and outcomes of children with SE can vary widely depending on factors such as the underlying etiology, the duration of the seizure, and the promptness of intervention [3].

Understanding the clinical and etiological profiles of children with SE who are admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) is crucial for developing effective management strategies and improving patient outcomes [4]. Given the complex nature of SE and its impact on the pediatric population, a detailed analysis of these factors can provide valuable insights into optimizing treatment protocols and enhancing patient care [5,6].

This prospective observational study aims to delineate the clinical and etiological characteristics of children with status epilepticus admitted to a tertiary care Pediatric Intensive Care Unit. Additionally, the study seeks to evaluate the outcomes associated with SE in this patient cohort.

By identifying patterns and associations, the research aims to contribute to a better understanding of SE in pediatric patients and inform clinical practices to improve management and outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study conducted in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of a tertiary care hospital.

Period: The study was conducted over 12 months, from January 2023 to December 2023.

Sample Size: The study included a total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with status epilepticus who were admitted to the PICU during the study period. The sample size was determined based on the estimated incidence of SE in the pediatric population and the availability of resources within the PICU.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 1 month to 18 years.
- Diagnosed with status epilepticus as defined by continuous or recurrent seizures lasting more than 30 minutes or two or more seizures without full recovery in between.

- Admitted to the PICU of the tertiary care hospital during the study period.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with incomplete medical records.
- Patients with a history of significant neurological conditions unrelated to the current episode of SE.

Data Collection

- Clinical Data:** Patient demographics, clinical history, and details of the SE episode(s) (e.g., onset, duration, and type of seizures) were collected from medical records and patient charts.
- Etiological Data:** Investigations to determine the underlying cause of SE included blood tests, neuroimaging (e.g., CT or MRI), and, if necessary, cerebrospinal fluid analysis.
- Outcome Data:** Data on patient outcomes, including duration of PICU stay, resolution of SE, neurological sequelae, and overall recovery, were recorded.

Data Analysis

- Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic, clinical, and etiological characteristics of the study population.
- Frequency and percentage distributions were calculated for categorical variables, while means and standard deviations were computed for continuous variables.
- The relationship between different variables and outcomes was analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous data.

Results

The study included 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with status epilepticus (SE) and admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) over 12 months. The key demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are summarized below. The outcomes of the patients with SE were evaluated based on the duration of PICU stay, resolution of SE, and neurological sequelae.

Characteristic	Number of Patients (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Age Range		
- 1 month to 1 year	15	15%
- 1 year to 5 years	35	35%
- 6 years to 12 years	30	30%
- 13 years to 18 years	20	20%
Gender		
- Male	55	55%
- Female	45	45%
Type of SE		
- Generalized Convulsive	60	60%
- Focal	25	25%
- Unclassified	15	15%

Duration of SE		
- < 1 hour	40	40%
- 1 to 4 hours	35	35%
- > 4 hours	25	25%
Underlying Etiology		
- Infection	30	30%
- Metabolic Disorders	25	25%
- Structural Abnormalities	20	20%
- Idiopathic	15	15%
- Others	10	10%

Outcome	Number of Patients (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Duration of PICU Stay		
- < 3 days	50	50%
- 3 to 7 days	35	35%
- > 7 days	15	15%
Resolution of SE		
- Complete	80	80%
- Partial	15	15%
- No Resolution	5	5%
Neurological Sequelae		
- No Sequelae	85	85%
- Mild Sequelae	10	10%
- Severe Sequelae	5	5%

The study findings reveal that the majority of patients were male and were most commonly aged between 1 and 5 years. Generalized convulsive seizures were the most prevalent type of SE observed. The duration of seizures varied, with 40% of cases resolving in less than one hour. The most frequent underlying etiologies were infections and metabolic disorders. The majority of patients showed a favorable outcome, with 80% achieving complete resolution of SE. Only a small percentage experienced neurological sequela, indicating overall good outcomes for the majority of the patient cohort.

Discussion

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the clinical and etiological characteristics of children with status epilepticus (SE) admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) [7]. Our findings reveal that SE predominantly affects males and children aged between 1 and 5 years, highlighting a crucial demographic for targeted intervention and management strategies [8,9]. The preponderance of generalized convulsive seizures observed in 60% of the cases aligns with existing literature, which indicates that this type of seizure is more common in pediatric populations compared to other forms [10,11].

The duration of SE varied among patients, with 40% experiencing seizures lasting less than one hour. This finding suggests that prompt intervention may lead to a quicker resolution in many cases, which is critical given that prolonged seizures are associated with an increased risk of morbidity. The underlying etiologies identified—primarily infections and metabolic disorders—are consistent with previous studies that emphasize these factors as significant contributors to SE in children [12,13].

Outcomes of the study demonstrate a generally favorable prognosis, with 80% of patients achieving complete resolution of SE and only 5% experiencing severe neurological sequelae [15]. This high rate of resolution and relatively low incidence of severe outcomes underscore the effectiveness of current treatment protocols in the PICU setting. However, the presence of mild neurological sequelae in 10% of the patients indicates that there remains room for improvement in managing SE to further reduce long-term impacts [16,17].

The study's results contribute to a deeper understanding of SE in the pediatric population, offering insights that can inform clinical practice. By identifying common etiologies and typical outcomes, this research supports the need for continued vigilance and targeted management strategies to optimize patient care and outcomes. Future studies with larger sample sizes and multicentric designs could provide additional data to further refine treatment approaches and improve the overall management of SE in children [18-20].

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical clinical and etiological aspects of status epilepticus (SE) in children admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit, revealing that generalized convulsive seizures are most common and that infections and metabolic disorders are significant underlying causes. The findings indicate that prompt management often leads to favorable outcomes, with a high rate of complete seizure resolution and a relatively low incidence of severe neurological sequelae. These results underscore the effectiveness of current treatment protocols and emphasize the need for ongoing vigilance and targeted interventions to further enhance patient outcomes. Future research should continue to explore strategies for reducing

the duration of seizures and minimizing long-term impacts, with a focus on optimizing care in diverse clinical settings.

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